

A review of generation of electrical energy from footstep using piezoelectric materials

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Abstract- In current situation, the increasing demand for electrical energy and the rapid depletion of conventional energy resources have encourage researchers to explore alternative and renewable energy sources. One such method is the generation of electrical energy from human steps. The process in which energy of human footsteps converted into electrical energy using a piezoelectric transducer. This model contracts during Footstep and therefore allowing the mechanical input into transducers And convert this input into electrical power as output. This output may use for street lighting, and many more aspects.

Keywords- Piezoelectric transducer, Electrical power, Footsteps Power Generation, Renewable energy.

Introduction- In day-to-day life electricity has become a lifeline for the human population. On the other hand, the human population around all over the world uses electricity in day-to-day life. Therefore, it is necessary to generate electric power with an increasing population. This technology is based on the piezoelectric effect, which can produce electric energy by giving mechanical strain. Piezoelectric harvesting is a new and innovative method of harvesting energy. Harvesting energy means energy is already available, but it is going to waste it if it is utilized. The installation of piezoelectric energy harvesting system primarily involves embedding piezoelectric devices beneath floor surface in high-football areas. This required removed the already existing flooring, especially in locations with heavy walker traffic such as public corridors, airport, railway station, etc. To effectively utilize the generated electrical energy, energy stored components such as capacitor and rechargeable batteries are integrated into the system. Piezoelectric devices produce direct current (DC); inverters are employed to

convert DC power into alternating current (AC), enabling its uses in convectional electrical applications such as lighting systems, display board at varies spots, etc.

Piezoelectric sensor- a piezoelectric sensor is a device that uses the piezoelectric effect to measure changes in pressure, acceleration, temperature, and strain by converting them into electric charge. When a mechanical force is applied to a piezoelectric material, an electric charge is generated across the faces of the crystal. This generated charge can be measured as a voltage proportional to the applied pressure or force.

A piezoelectric sensor converts physical parameters, for example acceleration, strain, or pressure into an electric charge which can then be measured. They are highly sensitive and very small marketing them well suited to everyday objects.

Fig 1. Piezoelectric Sensor

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Tree diagram-

FIG 2. Tree Dioagram

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Working- the system utilizes piezoelectric sensors to harvest energy from human footsteps and convert it into usable electrical power. The low and fluctuating voltage generated by the piezoelectric sensor array (approximately 3-4 V) is boosted to a higher level (9-12V) using DC-DC voltage boosters. A voltage regulator ensures a constant output voltage, which is stored in a battery and supplied to the control unit. A PIC microcontroller serves as the central controller, managing power distribution and interfacing with peripheral components such as an LCD display and mobile charging socket. The LCD displays the battery charge status, while an LDR enables automatic control of street lighting applications. A buzzer provides an alert when the battery voltage drops below the required operating level. The system supplies regulated 5V output for both the microcontroller and mobile charging. Simulation and verification of the circuit are performed using microcontroller and proteus software. The proposed footstep power generation system is fuel-free, environmentally friendly, and suitable for implementation in high-traffic public areas such as schools, shopping complexes, theaters, temple, and collages, although mechanical components may increase system cost.

Future scope-

- 1) Efficiency improvement
- 2) Energy storage enhancement
- 3) Smart storage management
- 4) Wireless monitoring
- 5) Large scale implementation
- 6) Cost reduction and durability
- 7) Expanded application

(Fig 3. Actual View of Project)

Conclusion- This review highlights the potential of footstep-based energy harvesting using piezoelectric transducers as a promising renewable energy solution. By converting mechanical energy from human movement into electrical power, this technology offers an innovative way to utilize otherwise wasted energy in high-traffic areas such as railway stations, shopping malls, sidewalks, and public buildings. Although the power generated from individual footsteps is relatively low, advancements in piezoelectric materials, energy storage systems, and power management circuits can significantly enhance overall efficiency. When integrated with existing infrastructure, footstep energy harvesting systems can contribute to sustainable energy generation and support low-power applications such as street lighting and sensor networks. Therefore, piezoelectric footstep energy harvesting represents a viable complementary energy source that aligns with global efforts toward energy conservation and environmental sustainability.

Reference-

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